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Pre-print article

The Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule: a new approach to modelling internal migration

A report on approaches to smoothing internal migration data for local authority districts in England and Wales

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1. Key points

- Internal migration has a strong age profile linked to important life-course transitions: some types of migration extend over a range of ages (childhood, “workforce”, retirement, old age), while others are concentrated at particular single year of age age groups (school and university enrolment and graduation)
- When looking at age schedules of internal migration we may wish to remove random noise that tends to obscure the underlying signal in migration phenomena that span an age group – this may be done by smoothing the difference between migration propensities between adjacent age groups
- If we are using migration age schedules in making population projections, we do not want to propagate random blips into the future, so a smoothed schedule may give a better projection than unsmoothed data
- At the same time, we need to be careful not to smooth single year peaks or troughs where these **are** meaningful, for example when they arise from enrolment and graduation from universities and boarding schools which tend to mass at specific age groups
- The Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule (MPMMS) proposed in this paper builds on the previous work of Rogers Raquillet and Castro (1978), who developed the concept of smoothed Model Migration Schedules, and Wilson (2010), who proposed the Student Peak Model Migration Schedule: a model that smooths across most age groups but allows a student peak to remain clearly visible
- The Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule set out in this paper allows for many peaks to enable modelling of distinctive flows at any age – for example, migration to boarding schools including elite public schools established over many centuries. These school often admit pupils at age 13, with an additional admission point at 16. 18 is the most common age for admission to university. At 19 and 20 students frequently switch between different types of student accommodation, sometimes in different local authority districts. Ages 21 and above often show migration for graduation and progression from or between universities as well as to work opportunities. Potentially, a peak could be added for any age group if there is reason to believe that migration propensity at that age regularly differs from adjacent age groups.
- A working version of MPMMS implemented in an MS Excel spreadsheet and programmed in Visual Basic, with sample data for England and Wales, can be found at: [doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7728313](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728313).

2. Description of the Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule and its antecedents

The Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule (MPMMS) described in this paper is an extension of the earlier work of Andrei Rogers and colleagues in the late 1970s and early 1980s at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis set out in Rogers, Raquillet and Castro (1978), and more recently developed by Tom Wilson when at the University of Queensland to include a student peak (Wilson, 2010).

Rogers et al. (1978) used a generalised additive model comprising several curves to represent migration trends at different ages. They began by modelling what they described as “pre labor force” [childhood] migration with a negative exponential curve and a “labor force” curve with a double exponential curve. They subsequently added a further double exponential curve to model “post labor force” [retirement] migration, and an exponential curve to model old age migration. They also included a constant to improve model fit. The concept of an age schedule of migration can be interpreted in the context of Courgeau (1985) and the theory of the life course. Whilst Rogers et al. focus mainly on the “labor force” there are many other drivers of internal migration, including education, family and household formation or dissolution, environmental preferences, changes in levels of affluence or deprivation, that may vary with age.

Wilson (2010) proposed the further addition of a student peak to reflect the very prominent peak in migration due to student enrolment observed in Australia and many developed nations. He suggested that others might wish to add further peaks if their data seemed to require it. That suggestion was one of the starting points of the work summarised in this paper. Wilson also introduced another development: the use of the three-parameter Peristera-Kostaki (2007) curve rather than the four-parameter double exponential to model both retirement and student peak migration.

The work which has led to this proposal was prompted by the need to model internal migration for England and Wales at local authority district level for the purpose of small area population projection. In many districts there are clearly at least two peaks for student enrolment and graduation migration, and in some many other persistent single-year-of-age features that need to be accounted for. Starting with Wilson’s model several approaches have been tried over several years leading to the version of the Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule (MPMMS) presented here. It is expected that further development may follow, including developing a model using the R environment (R core Team (2023)).

MPMMS is intended to model the age profile of internal migration at the level of local authority districts in England and Wales. It does this by smoothing those age ranges where there is no apparent reason to believe single-year-of-age peaks are required using a very similar approach to Rogers et al. (1978) and Wilson (2010) and treating observed

peaks as single-year-of-age groups to be excluded if there is good reason to believe these are regularly recurring features. Before presenting the MPMMS method we will look at its antecedents.

a. Rogers, Raquillet and Castro (1978) Model Migration Schedule

Rogers, Raquillet and Castro (1978) proposed a parameterised approach to modelling age schedules of migration using a generalised additive model comprising several curves to represent the varying levels of migration at different ages.

These initially comprised a “pre-labor force” or childhood curve and a “labor force” curve, with the option of a “post labor force” or retirement curve if required. A constant was included to improve model fit.

This model reflected the fact that the youngest children were quite likely to migrate but became decreasingly likely to do so as they got older. This was described as “pre-labor force migration”. It was modelled by a two-parameter negative exponential curve.

As young people approached adulthood there was a sharp rise in the likelihood of migration, peaking in the early twenties, and then a gradual decline over the earlier part of adulthood. This was described as “labor force migration”. This was modelled with a four-parameter double exponential curve (Coale and McNeil, 1972) – first rising steeply as young people joined the workforce, and then declining more gradually over adulthood.

A further curve was proposed that modelled slight rise and fall in migration around late middle age, often attributed to retirement. This was described as “post labor force migration”. This too was modelled with another four-parameter double exponential. The double parameter curves for “labor force” and “post labor force” migration were based on Coale and McNeil’s (1972) work on “age at first marriage”.

The whole schedule can be modelled with an eleven-parameter function (Rogers et al. 1978:493):

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{M}(x) = & a_1 \exp(-\alpha_1 x) \\ & + a_2 \{-\alpha_2 \exp(x - \mu_2) - \exp[-\lambda_2(x - \mu_2)]\} \\ & + a_3 \{-\alpha_3 \exp(x - \mu_3) - \exp[-\lambda_3(x - \mu_3)]\} \\ & + c \end{aligned}$$

where:

- a_1 height of childhood curve
- α_1 rate of descent of childhood curve
- a_2 height of “labor force” curve
- α_2 rate of ascent of “labor force” curve

μ_2	position of “labor force” curve
λ_2	rate of descent of “labor force” curve
a_3	height of retirement curve
α_3	rate of ascent of retirement curve
μ_3	position of retirement curve
λ_3	rate of descent of retirement curve
c	constant

The structure of that part of the equation dealing with the retirement curve is the same as that dealing with the “labor force” curve. The two curves would have been constrained in their position – with the “labor force” curve constrained in younger adulthood and the retirement curve constrained in later middle age.

Later Rogers and Watkins (1987) added a further curve to reflect the rising level of migration at the oldest ages. This comprised a two-parameter exponential curve. The full schedule was thus defined by thirteen parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{M}(x) = & a_1 \exp(-\alpha_1 x) \\ & + a_2 \{-\alpha_2 \exp(x - \mu_2) - \exp[-\lambda_2(x - \mu_2)]\} \\ & + a_3 \{-\alpha_3 \exp(x - \mu_3) - \exp[-\lambda_3(x - \mu_3)]\} \\ & + a_4 \exp(\alpha_4 x) \\ & + c \end{aligned}$$

Where the additional parameters are

a_4	height of old age curve
α_4	rate of ascent of old age curve

The rising level of migration observed among the elderly presumably driven by a need to access care was modelled with a final two-parameter exponential curve.

A constant was included to aid the general fit of the model. The following chart shows how the Rogers et al. model might work using recent data for all persons out migration from Rochdale.

The author’s representation of this model can be seen in Figure 1 (page 6).

The example in Figure 1 shows the Rogers et al. curves implemented in MS Excel using the constituent curves proposed for the model migration schedule above after Wilson (2010). The lozenges in Figure 1 show the values of the observed data for all persons out-migration from Rochdale. The childhood curve declines in a negative exponential, however the rate of decline is muted by the rising curve of the retirement curve. The workforce curve rises sharply from near zero at age 16, however it does not reach the student peak at 18, which appears as an outlier above the fitted curve. The labour force

curve provides a reasonable fit for the adult age range, aided by the retirement curve which mutes the rate of descent for in the younger adult ages, and lifts levels a little in the older adult range. It does not appear to model a retirement effect *per se* but it does help with the general fit. The old age rise in retirement propensity is well modelled by the old age curve. The constant in this case is close to zero. The constituent curves all follow Rogers et al. (1978) and Wilson (2010) (without the student peak).

Figure 1: Author’s example of the model migration schedule based on Rogers, Raquillet and Castro (1978) for all persons out-migration from Rochdale

As a model it does reasonably well but it is not able to model the extreme peak of out migration at 18, and it appears that early adulthood migration might be better modelled. In the 1970s mass participation in higher education had not taken off, and in any case the effect might not have been visible at inter-regional level in the USA. However English and Welsh districts in the 21st century present a different set of challenges – with strong movements of students between the ages of 18 and 22 in or out of virtually every district (Whyte, 2019).

b. Wilson's (2010) Student Peak Model Migration Schedule (SPMMS)

Wilson (2010) proposed adding another peak to the Rogers et al. (1978) framework – usually at or around age 18 – to represent the high level of migration observed at that age. This was proposed in relation to internal migration in Australia. By 2010 participation in higher education had increased substantially in the developed world and it continued to grow thereafter. HESA (2022) shows the scale of increase in the UK particularly amongst first degree and postgraduate (taught) students.

Figure 1 - First year higher education (HE) student enrolments by level of study
Academic years 2011/12 to 2020/21

Figure 2 (from HESA, 2022): HESA graphic showing the growth in student numbers in the UK

In addition to proposing the student peak Wilson made a change to the modelling of the retirement curve by using the three-parameter Peristera-Kostaki (2007) double exponential curve, rather than the four-parameter Coale-McNeil (1972) double exponential curve proposed by Rogers et al.. The Peristera-Kostaki curve has three parameters representing height, position and both the rate of ascent and descent – which are assumed to be the same.

Wilson (2010) used a Coale-McNeil (1972) double exponential curve to model the single student peak. This allowed for a sharp peak, usually at age 18, representing migration to university with some effects on the surrounding age groups.

The resulting equation was as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{M}(x) = & a_1 \exp(-\alpha_1 x) \\ & + a_2 \{-\alpha_2 \exp(x - \mu_2) - \exp[-\lambda_2(x - \mu_2)]\} \\ & + a_3 \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x - \mu_3}{\sigma_3}\right)^2\right] \\ & + a_4 \exp(\alpha_4 x) \\ & + a_5 \{-\alpha_5 \exp(x - \mu_5) - \exp[-\lambda_5(x - \mu_5)]\} \\ & + c \end{aligned}$$

Where the new parameters represent:

- a_3 height of the retirement curve
- μ_3 position of the retirement curve
- σ_3 rate of ascent and descent of the retirement curve
- a_5 height of the student peak
- α_5 rate of ascent of the student peak
- μ_5 position of the student peak
- λ_5 rate of descent of the student peak

(The ordering of the parameter follows Wilson (2010))

The following table and chart show how the Student Peak Model Migration Schedule might work with the same Rochdale data.

Figure 2: Author's example based on Wilson (2010)

Again, the example in Figure 2 uses the structure proposed by Wilson (2010), but was fitted with different software to his. Not only is the student peak (in red) a much better fit for the 18-year-old age group than in the model by Rogers et al. (1978), but it also improves the overall fit, particularly in young adulthood. A curve dedicated to dealing with the student peak allows the other curves to find their place amongst the observed datapoints. The double exponential curve used for the student peak makes a non-negligible contribution to other age groups, enabling the peak in migration at ages 17 and 18 to be better modelled and the descending slope of the workforce curve to find the central tendency of adult migration from 20 onwards.

Wilson's (2010) model incorporated a single student peak however he recognised that users may wish to model more than a single peak and invited them to extend the model to include further peaks if their data seemed to require them.

In the case of England and Wales peaks are required at age 18 and 21 in many districts to represent migration of school leavers to university at 18, and graduates at 21 to wherever they are next headed. Sometimes there are unusual features at other ages around those age groups: these will be explored later. In addition, in a small number of districts there are peaks of in-migration at 13 associated with "public schools" – fee-paying independent boarding schools such as Eton, Harrow and Winchester, and occasionally at other ages dependent on the admissions policies of various boarding schools. To smooth away these peaks (which represent real migration phenomena) would not be helpful for understanding what is going on, and if used for population projections could be misleading as the effect would be propagated cohort-wise over time. This research therefore extends the Wilson (2010) model to cope with the observed features of internal migration in England and Wales at local authority district level.

c. The principle of the Multiple Peak Model Migration schedule (MPMMS)

It was clear that in England and Wales at least one further student peak was required for nearly every local authority district: for example, a university town might see an out-flow of its own residents at 18 as they enrolled at university elsewhere, and then another out-flow at 21/22 when students typically graduate from a first degree, often returning to their "home" district, or moving on to employment or further study elsewhere.

At first it seemed that all that would be required would be to extend Wilson's (2010) spreadsheet by adding a worksheet to fit a second peak, and then further worksheets to fit other curves as necessary. In practice this proved difficult as each new peak had the potential to upset previously fitted curves, requiring a reversion to earlier sheets to correct. It also required considerable user discretion – which was fine if fitting a single set of data, but impractical if batch processing data for all local authority districts.

The next step involved checking the feasibility of fitting all the curves simultaneously. All the parameters for the constituent curves were placed on the spreadsheet and their values were iteratively changed by MS Excel's Solver add-in to minimise the sum of square difference between the observed data and fitted curve. This proved to work better than expected, and as the Multiple Peak Model Migration Schedule emerged this has been the principle followed.

Early attempts at modelling the schedules in this way often proved problematic. Sometimes the curves would emerge in entirely wrong places. Sometimes it would take an unacceptable time for the model to run and converge.

The solution to this (in general terms) was:

- a) to work from a good set of starting parameters
 - b) to set a small number of constraints on the values parameters could take, to prevent the retirement curve drifting off into the childhood age range for example
- and
- c) to simplify the structure of the model wherever possible. The result was a method which enabled the simultaneous modelling of all the curves.

The model also minimised the need for user judgement. It turned out this mostly yielded good results. Earlier versions of MPMMS considered adding further Peristera-Kostaki curves for age groups that ultimately extended from 16 to 22. With seven age groups modelled as additional peaks this added 14 variable parameters (height and rate of ascent/descent for each peak), with the parameter determining the position of each curve being fixed around the age in question. This worked, but often took over thirty seconds, sometimes as long as two minutes to converge and produce a result, which was typically characterised by some unnecessary uncertainty around the added peaks.

To deal with these shortcomings, a different approach was therefore adopted. Since each peak curve was being iteratively fitted using two parameters and each change in value potentially interacted with all the other values in the schedule, why not simply use the observed values for those peak years, and fit smoothed curves over the age ranges where there were rarely, if ever, any single-year-of-age peaks. This instantly produced an approach which works fast, and it usually produces a result which appears appropriate for the data at hand – the final fitted curve running through the middle of the observed data points.

d. A guided tour of MPMMS

A useful measure of internal migration proposed by Rogers et al. (1978) is the gross migraproduction rate. This is the sum of all the age-specific migration rates. It enables comparison of out-migration between local authorities, and over time. This measure does not work well for comparing in-migration, although it still works for rescaling values after curve fitting.

The current version of MPMMS uses the observed migration propensities (scaled to 1) for age groups 16 to 22. That is, each value in the observed data is divided by the sum of all the values, creating a new set of data where all the values sum to one. It applies a logical test to 13-year-old migration and fits it as an additional peak if the value of migration propensity at that age is by 5% or more greater than the average of the surrounding age groups (11, 12, 14, and 15). Otherwise, it is fitted as part of the childhood curve. The fitted curve can be rescaled by multiplying the scaled values by the gross migraproduction rate.

Childhood migration is fitted as a negative exponential curve, as in the predecessor models dating back to Rogers et al. (1978). There is one small change: in MPMMS childhood migration has its own constant. This is to help model represent the frequently observed flattening of the curve at about age five. This flattening could be because many parents become less inclined to move once their children start school.

The resulting equation for childhood migration is:

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{M}(x) &= a_1 \exp(-\alpha_1 x) \\ &+ c \\ &\text{(for ages } -1 \text{ to } 15)\end{aligned}$$

Where there appears to be a 13-year-old peak (where the 13-year-old value is more than 0.05 times the value of the average of the values for 11, 12, 14, and 15-year-olds) the propensity for that age group is excluded from the fitting process and the original (scaled to 1) value is used.

The “transition to adulthood” age range from 16 to 22 is not smoothed: the original (scaled to 1) values are used in recognition of the many unique single-year-of-age flows observed at that age range.

The young adult age range is modelled with a double-exponential curve as originally proposed by Rogers et al. (1978). Generally, migration propensities start high in the early twenties and decrease throughout the earlier part of the adult age range. In some cases only the descending part of the curve is used, although in some there is a need for an ascending section as well. This part of the schedule is modelled using the four-parameter Coale-McNeil (1972) double exponential, fitted over the ages 23 to 90.

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{M}(x) &= a_2 \{-\alpha_2 \exp(x - \mu_2) - \exp[-\lambda_2(x - \mu_2)]\} \\ &\text{(for ages } 23 \text{ to } 90)\end{aligned}$$

The retirement curve is modelled with a Peristera-Kostaki (2007) curve as proposed by Wilson (2010). For some districts this barely contributes anything, but in places such as Cornwall or Herefordshire, which are popular retirement destinations, it models the elevated migration seen between about 40 and 70. (Not all of this may be strictly related to retirement, but to seeking more environmentally attractive residential locations in later adulthood.) Old-age migration is modelled with an exponential curve as proposed by Rogers and Watkins (1987). The only difference is that the intercept for the slope is set at 90 rather than 0. This does not change the curve itself but helps in the interpretation of the height of the curve in old age, and in the event of experimentation by altering parameters manually. Thus the curve for ages 23 and above is modelled with the same curves as Wilson’s (2010) SPMMS.

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{M}(x) = & a_2\{-\alpha_2 \exp(x - \mu_2) - \exp[-\lambda_2(x - \mu_2)]\} \\ & + a_3 \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x - \mu_3}{\sigma_3}\right)^2\right] \\ & + a_4 \exp(\alpha_4 x) \\ & + a_5\{-\alpha_5 \exp(x - \mu_5) - \exp[-\lambda_5(x - \mu_5)]\} \\ & + c \end{aligned}$$

(for ages 23 to 90)

A number of examples of fitted schedules are shown below. First, for all internal migration in England and Wales – that is, all migration between one mid-year and the next from one local authority district to another, but not migration within a local authority district.

Figure 3: Internal Migration in England and Wales – all persons – 2018-2019

The observed data – converted to propensities and then scaled to one – are shown by the black lozenges. The fitted schedule is shown by a solid black line. The constituent curves of the adult age range are shown by various dashed lines. Based on a population of over 55 million, the original data is itself fairly smooth so there is not a great deal of work for MPMMS to do.

The negative exponential of the childhood age range from -1 (those born in-year) to 15 can be clearly seen. The gradient of the childhood curve flattens out at about 4 or 5, perhaps suggesting that many parents try to get their family migrations complete before school age.

A small, but significant peak can be seen at age 13, the common age for admission to public schools – elite boarding schools. MPMMS selected this as a peak because its value is more than 0.05 times that of the average of the four adjacent age groups.

There is an uptick at age 16, and further growth at 17. In fact 17 year-olds have a high propensity to migrate than any of the younger age groups.

The largest peak is observed at 18 – the most common age for admission to university and other higher education institutions. 18-year-olds in England are more migratory than any other single-year-of-age group.

Young people aged 19 and 20 are less likely to migrate, but nevertheless quite a lot of migration takes place at these ages, which show the fourth and fifth highest migration propensity in the schedule. There are likely to be many reasons for migration at this year – including students who have delayed enrolment to university, and young people moving for employment. However, there is evidence that some migration at 19 and 20 is related to a change in residential arrangements whilst at university, mainly between first year halls of residence, and second and third year private rented accommodation. This is particularly evident between Oadby & Wigston and Leicester, Wokingham and Reading, Broxstowe and Nottingham, Vale of White Horse and Oxford.

The second highest peak in the schedule is at 21, the most common age of graduation from a first degree. This is followed by the third most common age at 22. This could reflect those students who began a three-year degree at 19, or students who finish a four-year degree, a three year degree plus masters, or degree plus professional qualification.

Thereafter there appears to be a negative exponential curve reflecting declining propensity to migrate throughout early adulthood. Nevertheless, young adults remain more likely to migrate than do children of any age until they reach their mid-thirties. There are likely to be many reasons for this – including employment, family and household formation, environmental preferences, changes in types of accommodation (e.g. apartment to house).

Migration propensity continues to decline age-by-age until the mid-seventies, but the rate of decline slows – fifties and sixties. This could be what Rogers et al. (1978) describe as “post labor force” or retirement migration, or there could be a range of other things

that happen in middle age that might lead to migration – up-sizing or down-sizing of house type; change of household composition; marriage, separation or divorce; environmental preference (e.g. urban rural); changes in wealth (higher or lower income, accumulation of assets, inheritance, etc.).

From the mid-seventies migration propensities increase. This could be related to a greater need for health and social care, declining mobility, a desire to be closer to family members, changing environmental preferences, and similar considerations.

The life-course perspective (reference) could provide a theoretical framework to aid understanding of the schedule at national and local levels.

MPMMS allows the schedule to be smoothed, while retaining the detail for those age-groups where there seem to be specific single year of age phenomena. The value of this becomes more apparent when we look at individual local authority districts which frequently exhibit very specific features.

Figure 4: Birmingham in-migration – all persons – 2018 to 2019

Birmingham is the biggest local authority district in England and Wales (not including county councils which embrace multiple districts). The Birmingham schedule of in-migration shows some differences with the England and Wales schedule. Its student peaks at ages 18, 19, 20, 21 and 22 are higher than those for England and Wales. The peak at 18 reflects Birmingham’s role as a university city (Aston, Birmingham). It also seems to have a high level of 21-year-old in-migration, which is likely to include student returners, and graduates arriving to take up new opportunities in the city. There is no middle-aged lift in in-migration propensity – Birmingham is not seen as a retirement destination. It could be argued that Birmingham requires little help from MPMMS – the observed data itself is smooth.

Figure 5: Rutland in-migration – all persons – 2018 to 2019

Rutland is the third smallest district in England and Wales (after Isles of Scilly and City of London). The data is much noisier than that for England and Wales or Birmingham. The most prominent feature is the peak at age 13. It might be thought that this is a random “blip”, but in fact it reflects admission to the two large and long-established schools in the district, Oakham and Uppingham, which admit pupils of both sexes at that age. Further admissions are made to the sixth form at 16. The third peak at 21 is likely to be mainly student returners, however there are also military bases in Rutland which could be further drivers of young adult migration. Given these unusual factors, the relatively high levels of in-migration amongst middle aged adults may reflect Rutland’s environmental attractions – which include pleasant rural and market town areas, with easy access to Leicester, Peterborough, Nottingham and other major cities. Smoothing out the strange features in the transition to adulthood age range would probably be a mistake for Rutland, as would not smoothing the noise in the post-transition age range. In practice, for an district as small as Rutland it would be better to take an average of several years data and then smooth that.

The version of MPMMS provided alongside this paper includes data for all-persons migration (female and male) in 16 English local authority districts including the three smallest districts: Isles of Scilly, City of London, and Rutland. Their patterns are particularly noisy because of small sample sizes. A range of other districts are included from different authorities: large and small; university and non-university; north, midlands and south; deprived and affluent.

The data comes from the 2019 ONS detailed dataset for internal migration which covers migration between mid-year 2018 and mid-year 2019 (see Data Sources below for details). The counts of migrations were turned into propensities by dividing by the population at risk, which for most age groups would be the population at mid-year 2018. The number born during the year is estimated from the 2019 population. The population

estimates were provided by a NOMIS query (see Data Sources). MPMMS scales the propensities to total 1 across the full age range (those born during the year to those aged 90 and over at the start of the year). Scaling to one removes information about the quantum of migration and focusses attention on the shape of the curve. This is the practice which follows from Rogers et al. (1978). The fitted curve scaled to 1 can be rescaled to the observed values. The in-migration population at risk is that of the rest of England and Wales.

Total internal in-migration in England and Wales is also supplied. That comprises all migration from one English or Welsh district to another, but not migration within a district, or involving Northern Ireland or Scotland. All the other sample data can be regarded as a subset of the English and Welsh total data.

Readers are invited to experiment with the MS Excel model on Zenodo ([doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7728313](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728313)).

3. Conclusion

For the reasons outlined above it seems preferable to keep the original data for those age groups where there are unusual and unique dataflows in a district, particularly if these are recurring features that are observed year after year. Smoothing can then focus on those age ranges where there is no clear reason for migration propensity to mass at a particular age group: childhood and adulthood beyond the early twenties. Residential education appears to be the main driver of peaks at particular age groups. The transition to adulthood age range from 18 when young people acquire the majority of adult rights and responsibilities to 22 when most have completed tertiary education often exhibits strong local flows, where migration propensity at one age group bears little resemblance to adjacent year groups at local level. Trying to model these age groups using various exponential, negative exponential and double exponential curves seems unnecessary. To that end, MPMMS enables single ear age groups to be excluded from the smoothing process. Not only does it mean that these age groups simply use the observed data, it also seems to improve the fitting of curves at other age groups.

Further work

Work on MPMMS continues. A batch processing version is under development which enables the fitting of many datasets – e.g. all local authority districts, by sex, and for different time periods. This in turn enables common (and uncommon) features to be identified enabling a more sophisticated analysis of the characteristics of internal migration. When incorporated into a population projection system it may help prevent random noise propagating into future projected population numbers. It is hoped that a similar model will be produced using the R environment (R Core Team (2023)) over the coming months. Once a full set of smoothed schedules is produced then further work on the analysis and forecasting of internal migration can follow.

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Data sources

For counts of internal migration by age, sex, origin, and destination districts:

[Internal migration: detailed estimates by origin and destination local authorities, age and sex - Office for National Statistics \(ons.gov.uk\)](#)

For mid-year estimates by age sex and local authority district:

[Nomis - Official Census and Labour Market Statistics \(nomisweb.co.uk\)](#)